

An addition to researchers' toolkit: Algorithm-based facial expression analysis in L2 education

Joona Juselius, Pentti Henttonen, Mariel Wuolio, and Anna von Zansen

University of Helsinki

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Contents

1	Introduction	3
1.1	What is Algorithm-based Facial Expression Analysis?	3
1.2	How do facial expressions convert to analyzable numbers?	3
1.3	Example use cases	3
1.3.1	Use case 1	3
1.3.2	Use case 2	4
1.3.3	Use case 3	4
1.3.4	Use case 4	5
1.4	How to conduct?	6
2	Step 1: Recording video material	6
2.1	Setting up Interlab for data collection	6
2.1.1	Video recorder placement	6
2.1.2	Video camera settings	7
2.2	Data storage	7
2.2.1	Group storage	7
2.2.2	File paths on Interlab computer	7
3	Step 2: Running Py-Feat Software	8
3.1	Creating input folder for your videos	8
3.2	Running Py-Feat for facial Action Unit extraction	10
4	Step 3: Visualizing Py-Feat output	12
4.1	Tables	12
4.2	Visualizations	14
4.2.1	AU activation averages and emotion time-series	14
4.2.2	Cluster visualizations and data tables	15
4.2.3	Landmark videos	18
5	Literature	19

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1 Introduction

1.1 What is Algorithm-based Facial Expression Analysis?

The aim of algorithm-based facial expression analysis is to convert research participants' facial expressions and facial muscle movements into facial Action Units (see Table 1), which contain numerical values that can later be analyzed.

Rather than using a slow human rater, a trained computer algorithm compares the predicted values of facial muscle contractions to a larger dataset, and renders estimates of expressions and muscle movements (see 1.2.).

The results can provide useful information about, for example, the participants' mental states (e.g. happiness, surprise, fear, neutral), how focused they were, and how pleasant or unpleasant they viewed the situation.

The algorithm toolbox used in this manual is Py-Feat: Python Facial Expression Analysis Toolbox (Cheong et al., 2023), which has provided reliable results for research use.

This addition to researcher's handbook provides guiding steps to conduct an algorithm-based facial expression analysis using the recording equipment and the advanced and powerful computers that are conveniently available in Interlab.

1.2 How do facial expressions convert to analyzable numbers?

Paul Ekman and Wallace V. Friesen (1978) developed Facial Action Coding System (FACS), which is considered as the gold standard for objective measurement of facial movement. Their system focuses on the activation intensity of the facial muscles during the time of observation.

The central components of the system are facial Action Units (AUs) (see table 1), which represent the contraction or relaxation of certain facial muscles or muscle groups. When these AUs are combined, any human facial expression can be described. For example, a genuine smile usually involves AU06 (**Cheek Raiser**) and AU12 (**Lip Corner Puller**).

When a computer algorithm, such as Py-Feat analyzes a facial image or video, it converts the visual movement into numbers based on the predicted intensity of the muscle contractions. For most muscles, the algorithm provides a decimal value between 0.00–0.01. Thus, the value 0.00 means that the muscle is totally relaxed, whereas 1.00 indicates the muscle is in maximum possible contraction, and value of 0.50 means medium activation of the AU. For three AUs: AU07 (**Lid Tightener**), AU11 (**Nasolabial Deepener**), and AU20 (**Lip Stretcher**) the software only provides a binary estimation. It simply reports whether the contraction is detected (1) or not detected (0) (Cheong et al., 2023).

The intensities of the AU activations are in this manual also portrayed as a five-step scale that ranges from A (trace of contraction) to E (maximum contraction) (see table 2) (Cheong et al., 2023).

However, algorithm-based facial expression analysis has received critique that the algorithms consistently demonstrate performance biases, which yield less accurate emotion readings that depend on the participants's skin tone and gender identity. Moreover, when researchers use the software, they are forced to implicitly accept the tool's built-in psychological assumptions, which often oversimplify how human emotion actually works. In light of this, it has been suggested that before trusting an algorithm-based output, researchers must investigate the specific datasets used to train the machine learning algorithm to ensure it is unbiased and appropriate for their specific subject pool (Cross et al., 2023). To achieve this, we recommend reading Cheong et al.'s (2023) Py-Feat: Python Facial Expression Analysis Toolbox.

Note: Please be aware that the emotion estimates that Py-Feat produces are for research use only. Other use is strictly prohibited.

1.3 Example use cases

Algorithm-based facial expression analysis is widely used in the academic fields of psychology, cognition sciences, and education sciences. To further illustrate the method, this chapter contains summaries of five recent example use cases.

1.3.1 Use case 1

Chong and Aryadoust (2023) investigates a test-taker's oral language ability when it is combined with their facial emotional expressions and the characteristics of the test stimuli. The participants

were 60 bilingual university undergraduate students in Asia with English as their first language, and the evaluators were four trained graduate students who were acting as raters to assess the spoken responses.

The material was collected using a computer setup. First, the participants were seated to watch or listen to two minutes of stimuli that was varied in modality (in this case audio or video), and sentiment, which was designed to evoke happiness or sadness. Next, the participants answered orally to 12 follow-up questions to examine their comprehension. Finally, the evaluators graded their responses.

In the analysis, the evaluator data was validated through Multi-facet Rasch measurement, and the facial expression data was extracted using FaceReader software, which uses similar frame-by-frame facial Action Unit and emotion recognition algorithms as Py-Feat.

The key findings indicate that the modality and sentiment of the stimuli manipulated facial responses successfully. Participants who reacted to video and 'happy' stimuli evoked significantly greater amounts of measurable facial emotions compared to audio formats or 'sad' stimuli. Furthermore, despite the variations in induced emotion and test format, neither the sentiment nor the modality had any significant effect on the participants' actual speaking performance scores.

1.3.2 Use case 2

Burton (2024) examines the influence of nonverbal behavior and facial expressions on the scoring of second language proficiency during speaking assessments.

The material of the study was video recordings of 30 participants of varied language proficiency levels who took an international high-stakes language test. After this, a group of 100 novice raters evaluated video samples that were cut from the material. The duration of each sample was two minutes, and the raters were instructed to focus on four criteria: fluency, vocabulary, grammar, and comprehensibility.

Next, nonverbal behaviors, visual attention and emotional valence (positive or negative emotions) were extracted with iMotions software, which uses similar frame-by-frame facial Action Unit and emotion recognition algorithms as Py-Feat. Finally, the scoring of the raters was compared with the results of the iMotion facial expression analysis.

The key findings suggest that nonverbal behavior does impact scores, but the effect is heavily dependent on the speaker's proficiency. Most notably, positive emotional behavior (higher mean valence) improved comprehensibility scores for the lower-proficiency group. On the contrary, these effects were completely absent in the higher performing group. From this angle, the research shows quantifiable evidence that visual and affective cues are subconsciously linked with linguistic evaluation.

1.3.3 Use case 3

Seikavandi et al. (2025) explores the temporal dynamics of facial mimicry, often described as unconscious imitation of facial expressions of another humans. The aim is to seek correlations with how humans manage their emotional information, and how this mimicry fluctuates across different emotions and personality traits.

The study uses data collected from the AFFEC (Advancing Face-to-Face Emotion Communication) multimodal dataset, which features 73 participants recorded over multiple trials of simulated emotional dialogues that include the widely used six distinct emotions: anger, disgust, fear, happiness, neutral, and sad.

Table 1: Summary of 20 key facial Action Units (AU)

Action Unit	Description	Action Unit	Description
AU01	Inner Brow Raiser	AU14	Dimpler
AU02	Outer Brow Raiser	AU15	Lip Corner Depressor
AU04	Brow Lowerer	AU17	Chin Raiser
AU05	Upper Lid Raiser	AU20	Lip Stretcher
AU06	Cheek Raiser	AU23	Lip Tightener
AU07	Lid Tightener	AU24	Lip Pressor
AU09	Nose Wrinkler	AU25	Lips Part
AU10	Upper Lip Raiser	AU26	Jaw Drop
AU11	Nasolabial Deepener	AU28	Lip Suck
AU12	Lip Corner Puller	AU43	Eyes Closed

Table 2: Summary of AU Activation Intensities

Grade	Description
A	A trace of muscle contraction
B	Slight muscle contraction
C	Pronounced muscle contraction
D	Severe muscle contraction
E	Extreme or maximum muscle contraction

Next, a set of 17 key Facial Action units was extracted using OpenFace 2.0, which uses similar frame-by-frame facial Action Unit and emotion recognition algorithms as Py-Feat. In addition, Dynamic Time Warping (DTW) was used to standardize timing across samples, and to reveal patterns that can be completely missed by frame-by-frame analysis.

The key findings illustrate that the intensity of facial mimicry is highly specific to the emotion presented. The participants demonstrated greater mimicry for the emotion of 'fear' compared to 'happy', as well as reduced mimicry for 'anger' compared to 'fear'.

1.3.4 Use case 4

Zang and Yang (2025) studied the connection between a person's self-esteem and their continuous and shifting facial expressions during active social engagement. The material was video recordings of 211 participants who performed a public self-introduction task.

The participants were recorded on video while presenting themselves. Next, their baseline self-esteem was concurrently measured using a standard psychological survey (the Rosenberg Self-Esteem Scale). Then, the facial Action Units was extracted using OpenFace 2.0 software, which uses similar frame-by-frame facial Action Unit and emotion recognition algorithms as Py-Feat.

After this, OpenFace software 'translated' these Action Units into four primary emotions: happiness, sadness, fear, and disgust. The research team then applied time-series analysis to track how these emotions fluctuated over the duration of the presentation. Finally, machine learning algorithms and explainable AI (SHAP) were used to map these dynamic visual patterns against the participants' self-reported self-esteem scores.

The key findings imply that the dynamic fluctuations of all four basic emotions that the algorithm interpreted from the participants' facial expressions were strongly linked to an individual participant's self-esteem. Notably, the way participants managed or displayed negative emotional expressions, such as disgust, sufficed as a significant predictor of their lower self-esteem levels. Therefore, facial expressions may reveal high self-esteemed individuals from their common emotion expression style, which lacks the facial markers of negative emotions.

Figure 1: Algorithm-based facial expression analysis in three simple steps

1.4 How to conduct?

This handbook was designed to give the reader a simple yet productive and effective workflow to conduct competent algorithm-based facial expression analysis. The instructions cover many important steps from research preparations to the point of analysis.

After the preparations are done, the main part of this handbook walks the user through the process of algorithm-based facial expression analysis in three simple steps (see fig. 1).

STEP 1 Advice on how to record video and audio material in Interlab. This includes setting up the recorders and their placement to find recording angles suitable for facial expression extraction, limiting factors such as lightning and possible obstructions, and where to store the recordings before and after the facial expression extraction.

STEP 2 Advice on how to extract facial muscle activations from the videos. Simple step-by-step instructions on how to run Py-Feat to extract facial action units (AU) data on Interlab computer. The computer can be left alone to compute the analysis, which can take several hours to complete. Once finished, the outputs can be found inside a folder for further processing.

STEP 3 Advice on how to visualize the Py-Feat output files. For the most basic analysis, we provide a simple pipeline to convert the outputs to Excel and to visualize the results.

Visualizations, such as graphs and facial action unit activation videos, may help to understand the data with a single look and provide fast snapshots to possible findings depending on the research question. While the algorithms are deemed to be precise, a quality control check should be done when working with fully automated processes.

Finally, after this step the user has everything needed to conduct an analysis for their research. As an extra precaution, the final chapter of the handbook covers the safe archiving or disposal of the data, since the analyzed facial expressions are sensitive biometric measurements.

2 Step 1: Recording video material

2.1 Setting up Interlab for data collection

2.1.1 Video recorder placement

Angle As facial recognition algorithms can be quite sensitive to facial feature obtrusions in the video, the best practice is to record the participants facing the camera directly. The tripods in Interlab are easy to move to a preferred angle, and the height of the camera can be adjusted to the participant's face level. The ideal recording angle is parallel to the one often seen in passport or identification card pictures, which is the eye-level of the participant. The recording distance is optimal if the face of the participant covers around 25–30% of the screen.

Lighting With lighting, it is important to find the right balance. Too bright or too dim lighting conditions may reduce the algorithm's ability to recognize facial landmarks. Shadows cast by eyebrows or the nose can also affect the analysis negatively. Interlab has LED work lights that can be assembled to adjust the lighting accordingly. Generally, a low to medium level extra illumination is often sufficient, when it originates from an angle that does not dazzle the participant. However, the light should be direct and perpendicular to the face. Try to avoid light sources behind the participant as they may leave the face too dark.

Eyeglasses, long hair, facial hair Eyelasses are one of the most common sources of error because they affect the eye and eyebrow area, which are central to the recognition of almost all basic emotions. If the lenses reflect light, the algorithm cannot recognize the eyes or the position of the eyelids. Tilt the light source or ask the participant to tilt the glasses slightly downwards to remove the reflection from the camera line. Moreover, thick eyeglass frames can cover the eyebrows completely. Eyebrow movement is essential for emotion detection. If possible, prefer rimless glasses or ask the subject to wear contact lenses.

Long hair can confuse the algorithm models and distort the intensity of facial expressions, since the forehead area is critical for several AUs. For example, surprise requires the detection of the entire forehead frown and eyebrow raise. If hair cover this area, the algorithm may only register

Figure 2: File paths on Interlab computer

a neutral expression. Hair should be pulled away from the forehead and, for example, put behind the ears. Algorithms use the edges of the face (jawline and temples) to determine the position of the head. If hair covers the chin or cheeks, the algorithm may think the head is in a different position than it actually is, which distorts the proportions of the facial expressions.

The beard is the most challenging element because it obscures the AUs around the mouth, such as the raising or lowering of the corners of the mouth. Most algorithm models detect the edges of the mouth. A thick mustache or beard can completely hide the micro-movements of the corners of the mouth. The beard masks the lowering or tension of the jaw. If the subject has a beard, it is even more important that the lighting comes from directly in front so that the shadows of the beard do not mix with the shadows of the mouth.

2.1.2 Video camera settings

Resolution Usually, 720p (1280x720) or 1080p (1920x1080) will suffice. Higher resolutions (4K) may also be recorded, but the benefits are often minimal.

FPS To capture frame-by-frame micro-expressions, it is recommended to record at least 24–30 frames per second.

2.2 Data storage

2.2.1 Group storage

One of the many perks when working at Interlab is that the computer is connected to the university networks. You can access your personal **Z-drive** as well as the group storage folders (commonly known as **P-drive**) with the computer’s **File Explorer**. This means the files targeted for Py-Feat analysis can be downloaded from the network to the Interlab computer, which is both convenient and secure when dealing with sensitive data. The recorded (or pre-recorded) material travels fast through the network and is ready to use within a brief moment.

2.2.2 File paths on Interlab computer

Algorithm-based facial expression analysis requires that the video or image files must be temporally stored in the hard drive of the Interlab computer. The figures 2 and 3 show where you should upload the video or image files you want to analyze with Py-Feat. These graphs are here for later use should you need to quickly check the locations of the files. Please note, the automated process creates all output files in the designated **output** folder, therefore you only need to follow the instructions in chapter 3 to create the **input** folder.

Figure 3: Tree figure of the file paths on Interlab computer

3 Step 2: Running Py-Feat Software

Note: Please be aware that Py-Feat analysis might take several hours to complete. One minute of video (25 fps) takes ≈ 30 minutes (15 minutes of video ≈ 7.5 hours)

Follow these steps to run Py-Feat to extract facial action units from your source videos.

3.1 Creating input folder for your videos

1. Login to the Interlab computer using your personal university credentials
2. Open **File Explorer** and navigate to `C:\hyapp\facial_expression_analysis`

3. Double-click `01_Create_input_folder.bat`

3.1. The program creates a folder `C:\LocalData\\input` and verifies it is in that location.

3.1.1. Run this program after each login whether you have previously created the folder or not. This is to ensure that the input folder is in the correct location, which is required by the process.

3.2. Press any key to close the window

4. Copy (drag and drop) the video or image file(s) you want Py-Feat to analyze into the fresh **input** folder

4.1. Multiple videos or images can be queued for analysis

4.1.1. You may create other folders inside the folder as you please, but ensure the input folder contains the media to be analyzed

4.2. For videos, use `.mp4`, `.mov`, `.avi`, or `.mkv` formats

4.3. For images, use `.jpg`, `.jpeg`, `.png`, `.gif`, `.tiff`, or `.raw` formats

3. Read processing time estimates from the **Command Prompt**, the format is mm:ss

3.1. The program shows a frequently updated progress bar and percentage for the video in process as well as for all videos


```
C:\WINDOWS\system32\cmd. x + v - □ x
Loading Py-Feat detector... 100%
(Detector device: cpu)
Skipping every None frame(s), analyzing 1 frame(s) simultaneously
Found 1 video(s) to analyze
All videos: 0%|
Processing: Video2.mp4
4%|
| 0/1 [00:00<?, ?file/s]
| 6/157 [00:18<07:18, 2.91s/it]
```

4. You may leave the computer to process the files as the task might take several hours to complete

5. When the **Command Prompt** confirms the process was completed (All videos 100%), a summary is displayed


```
Command Prompt x + v - □ x
All videos: 0%|
Processing: Video.mp4
100%|
Saved: C:/LocalData/joonajus/input/output/Video_video_pyfeat.csv
All videos: 33%|
Processing: Video1.mp4
100%|
Saved: C:/LocalData/joonajus/input/output/Video1_video_pyfeat.csv
All videos: 67%|
Processing: Video2.mp4
100%|
Saved: C:/LocalData/joonajus/input/output/Video2_video_pyfeat.csv
All videos: 100%|
3/3 [27:10<00:00, 543.34s/file]
Summary:
Videos - Analyzed: 3 | Failed: 0 | Total: 3
Outputs saved in: C:\LocalData\joonajus\input\output
Press any key to continue . . .
```

5.1. Check that all videos were processed without errors (**Failed: 0**)

5.2. Outputs were saved in: C:\LocalData\\input\output

5.3. Press any key to close the active window

5.4 In the rare case of failures, please check the format of the video (mp4, mov, avi, and mkv are compatible) and relaunch 02_run_py-feat.bat

5.5 Py-Feat output files are in CSV (comma separated values) format. Depending on the length of your analyzed video, the size of each file can be >20 or even >100 megabytes.

6. Collect the yourfilename_pyfeat.csv files from the output folder in your input folder (or copy the whole folder) to your desired location (e.g. P-drive, Umpio, external hard drive, USB stick) or proceed to visualize the outputs in **Step 3 (5.2)** (in this case, do not move the files)

Step 2 of the process is now complete!

4 Step 3: Visualizing Py-Feat output

4.1 Tables

Py-feat delivers its output in comma separated values (CSV) form. If you open the file in Excel, the data looks unorganized and raw. The file, however, can be accessed in another software such as R without any alterations.

Follow these steps to format the output for compatibility with Excel

1. Double-click a CSV file (yourfilename_pyfeat.csv) to open it in Excel
2. Select the first column (A) by clicking it

3. Then click the **Data** heading and select **Text to Columns**

4. Next, a new window opens

- 4.1. Click **Next** >

4.2. Place a tick in Comma

4.1. Click Finish

5. Data is now in standardized and accessible layout

6. Save the file as a new **Excel** file
7. Repeat the process for the remaining CSV files (if necessary)

4.2 Visualizations

Visualizations provide aid to interpret the massive numerical data which Py-Feat analysis creates. We have compiled a set of basic graphs to visualize your Py-Feat output. The graphs are plotted using a Python script which draws and places them in thematically (e.g. AU activation averages, emotion time series) separated folders in the **output** folder.

4.2.1 AU activation averages and emotion time-series

Follow these steps to visualize AU activation averages and emotion time-series from your Py-Feat output

1. Navigate to C:\hyapp\facial_expression_analysis
2. Double-click the file 03_Visualize.bat

2.1. 03_Visualize.bat launches **Command Prompt** and runs Python to visualize all Py-Feat outputs in the **output** folder. Once the batch is processed, a set of new folders is created in the **output** folder.

2.2. This process is much faster than Py-Feat analysis, usually takes ~ a few seconds to a minute

```

C:\WINDOWS\system32\cmd. x + v
Creating visualizations...

Saved plot for: Video1_video_pyfeat
Saved emotion time-series plot for: Video1_video_pyfeat
Saved plot for: Video2_video_pyfeat
Saved emotion time-series plot for: Video2_video_pyfeat
Saved plot for: Video_video_pyfeat
Saved emotion time-series plot for: Video_video_pyfeat
Processing files: 100%| 3/3 [00:03<00:00, 1.02s/file]

All visualizations saved in your output folder
Press any key to continue . . . |

```

3. When **Command Prompt** confirms the process was completed, press any key to close the active window

4. Collect yourfilename_pyfeat.png files (or the folders containing the files) from the **output** folder to your desired location (e.g. P-drive, Umpio, external hard drive, USB stick)
This process is now complete.

4.2.2 Cluster visualizations and data tables

As discussed earlier, facial expressions are rarely the result of a single AU activation. For example, an authentic or "Duchenne" smile requires both the AU12 (Lip Corner Puller) and the AU06 (Cheek Raiser) to be activated simultaneously.

We created a program that allows you to define these multi-AU combinations as "clusters" and treat them as a single event. It automatically investigates if all required AUs (selected by you) are active at the same time, which is practical if you need to verify if a participant exhibits specific facial expressions.

The program visualizes the AUs in a heatmap figure that provides a time-series map of a participant's emotional journey. You can instantly see if their reactions become more frequent or intense over time (e.g., shows emotional fatigue or increasing frustration).

With a high-contrast colormap (magma) and inactive moments masked in black, the most relevant data pops up visually in pale yellow. However, blank frames (when Py-Feat did not recognize a face in the frame) are left white. Moreover, the program translates raw frame numbers into time-based metrics that are ready for your further analysis. Additionally, it calculates the active proportion (%), which is far more useful for comparison than raw frame counts, and provides both mean and median intensities for the entire set(s) of AU or emotion clusters.

Follow these steps to generate an AU cluster heatmap and a statistics data table

1. Navigate to C:\hyapp\facial_expression_analysis
2. Double click 04_Cluster_viz.bat
3. The program now prompts you for several parameters to customize the analysis:
 1. Enter the frame per second value of the original video. This value helps the program to calculate precise time intervals for the heatmaps and statistics.

```

C:\WINDOWS\system32\cmd. x + v
Enter original video fps (e.g. 24 or 29.97):

```

2. Cluster definition:

- Enter the target AUs for a specific expression or AU movement you want to explore (e.g., AU06, AU12 for a smile).

```
C:\WINDOWS\system32\cmd. x + v
Enter original video fps (e.g. 24 or 29.97): 24
Enter target AUs for Cluster 1 separated by comma (e.g. AU06, AU12) (or press Enter to stop): |
```

- Assign a name to this group (e.g., "Duchenne smile"). If you leave it blank, the name defaults to just "Cluster X".

```
C:\WINDOWS\system32\cmd. x + v
Enter original video fps (e.g. 24 or 29.97): 24
Enter target AUs for Cluster 1 separated by comma (e.g. AU06, AU12) (or press Enter to stop): AU06, AU12
Enter name for this cluster (e.g. Duchenne smile) or press Enter for 'Cluster 1': |
```

- You can define multiple clusters sequentially. Press **Enter** on an empty line to finish.

```
C:\WINDOWS\system32\cmd. x + v
Enter original video fps (e.g. 24 or 29.97): 24
Enter target AUs for Cluster 1 separated by comma (e.g. AU06, AU12) (or press Enter to stop): AU06, AU12
Enter name for this cluster (e.g. Duchenne smile) or press Enter for 'Cluster 1': Sm
ile
Enter target AUs for Cluster 2 separated by comma (e.g. AU06, AU12) (or press Enter to stop): |
```

- (Optional) Enter the column name of a specific emotion (e.g., happiness) to include it in the heatmap and average intensity calculations for comparison.

```
C:\WINDOWS\system32\cmd. x + v
Enter original video fps (e.g. 24 or 29.97): 24
Enter target AUs for Cluster 1 separated by comma (e.g. AU06, AU12) (or press Enter to stop): AU06, AU12
Enter name for this cluster (e.g. Duchenne smile) or press Enter for 'Cluster 1': Sm
ile
Enter target AUs for Cluster 2 separated by comma (e.g. AU06, AU12) (or press Enter to stop):
Enter target emotion for comparison e.g. happiness (press Enter to skip): |
```

- Define a threshold when an AU cluster is considered "active." You can enter:
 - A decimal between 0.00 and 1.00.
 - A letter grade of intensity (starting at): **A** (0.01), **B** (0.16), **C** (0.26), **D** (0.58), or **E** (0.90).

```
C:\WINDOWS\system32\cmd. X + v
Enter original video fps (e.g. 24 or 29.97): 24
Enter target AUs for Cluster 1 separated by comma (e.g. AU06, AU12) (or press Enter to stop): AU06, AU12
Enter name for this cluster (e.g. Duchenne smile) or press Enter for 'Cluster 1': Smile
Enter target AUs for Cluster 2 separated by comma (e.g. AU06, AU12) (or press Enter to stop):
Enter target emotion for comparison e.g. happiness (press Enter to skip): happiness
Enter activation threshold (0.00-1.00) or intensity value (-, A, B, C, D, E): |
```

4. Once the process is complete, you can press any key to continue and check the `input\output\feature_output` directory for the following:

```
C:\WINDOWS\system32\cmd. X + v
Enter original video fps (e.g. 24 or 29.97): 24
Enter target AUs for Cluster 1 separated by comma (e.g. AU06, AU12) (or press Enter to stop): AU06, AU12
Enter name for this cluster (e.g. Duchenne smile) or press Enter for 'Cluster 1': Smile
Enter target AUs for Cluster 2 separated by comma (e.g. AU06, AU12) (or press Enter to stop):
Enter target emotion for comparison e.g. happiness (press Enter to skip): happiness
Enter activation threshold (0.00-1.00) or intensity value (-, A, B, C, D, E): C
Heatmap saved: C:\LocalData\joonajus\input\output\feature_output\smile\speaker025_smile_thld_0.26_heatmap.png

Summary saved: C:\LocalData\joonajus\input\output\feature_output\smile\metrics_summary_smile_thld_0.26.csv
You may now close this window.
Press any key to continue . . . |
```

1. Activation heatmap figures (.png)

- The heatmap figures visualize AU cluster and optional emotion intensities over time with the `magma` (black-to-yellow) colormap.
- Cluster rows will appear black when the activation threshold is not met by all AUs in that cluster.
- White clusters indicate empty columns with no Py-Feat data.
- The X-axis displays time in `MM:SS` format based on the provided FPS.

2. Metrics summary (.csv)

- The program generates a summary file that uses a semicolon (;) separator and a comma (,) decimal for compatibility with **Excel**.
- The data columns include important information such as total duration, active frames, proportion of activation, and mean/median intensities for AU clusters and emotions.

5. In the case of errors

1. If the program skips a CSV file, please verify that it contains all the target AU names (e.g. AU06, AU12) you entered in the beginning of the process.
2. If the program prompts you with a "Permission denied" warning, please make sure the summary CSV is not open in another program (**Excel**) when the program tries to save new results. Close the file (in **Excel**) and press enter again.

4.2.3 Landmark videos

We also created a program, which converts Py-Feat analyzed data into a graphical video. It uses CSV files that contain facial Action Units (AUs), and renders a stylized face that visually contracts its muscles and tracks psychological metrics, such as valence in real time.

It checks the intensity of the AU associated with each muscle and fills them with colors in accordance with the intensity grading scale. The grades from C to E range from light blue (pronounced activity) to dark blue (maximum activity).

The video helps you to understand how the algorithm sees the AUs while illustrating them on a simple model face that anonymizes the participant by not revealing their actual and individual facial proportions.

Follow these steps to render a landmark video of the CSV data

1. Navigate to C:\hyapp\facial_expression_analysis
2. Double click 05_Landmark_video.bat
3. The program now prompts you to enter the frame per second value of the original video. This value helps the program to calculate precise time intervals for the landmark video.


```
C:\WINDOWS\system32\cmd. x + v
Enter original video fps (e.g. 24 or 29.97):
```

4. Read processing time estimates from the **Command Prompt**, the format is mm:ss

4.1. The program shows a frequently updated progress bar and percentage for the video in process.


```
C:\WINDOWS\system32\cmd. x + v
Enter the fps value of your original video (e.g. 24 or 29.97): 24
Processing: WolfgangLanger_Pexels_video_pyfeat.csv
Rendering WolfgangLanger_Pexels_video_pyfeat: 14% | 64/472 [00:04:00:28, 14.18it/
```

4. Once the process is complete, you can press any key to continue and check the input\output\landmark_videos directory for a video with file name ending in landmark_video.mp4:


```
C:\WINDOWS\system32\cmd. x + v
Enter the fps value of your original video (e.g. 24 or 29.97): 24
Processing: WolfgangLanger_Pexels_video_pyfeat.csv
Rendering WolfgangLanger_Pexels_video_pyfeat: 100% | 472/472 [00:35<00:00, 13.16it
Saved: C:/LocalData/joonajus/input/output/landmark_videos/WolfgangLanger_Pexels_vide
o_pyfeat_landmark_model.mp4
Press any key to continue . . . |
```

Step 3 of the process is now complete!

5 Literature

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